

Effect of Influencer-Led Body Positivity Social Media Content on Eating Disorder Risk among Undergraduates of Osun State University and Redeemer's University

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Abstract

Despite the increasing prominence of the body-positivity movement on social media, limited Nigerian research has examined the influence of influencer-led body-positivity content on young adults' body-image perception and eating behaviours. This study addressed this gap by assessing the perceived impact of influencer-led body-positivity content on body-image perception among undergraduates and determining its association with self-reported disordered eating behaviours. A cross-sectional survey design was employed. The population comprised undergraduates of Osun State University and Redeemer's University. Multi-stage sampling was used to select 391 respondents, representing various faculties, with a 98.9% response rate. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analysed with descriptive statistics. Findings indicated exposure to influencer-led body-positivity content, with 47.8% viewing it three to five times weekly and 27.6% daily. While 30.9% perceived such content as genuine and empowering, 45.2% described it as motivational but unrealistic. Behaviourally, 40.1% reported dieting or restricting intake, 27.6% skipped meals, 20.4% felt guilty after eating, and 7.9% engaged in binge eating. Influencer body type (57.0%) was the most cited factor shaping content interpretation and weight-loss success stories (30.4%) were the most influential in altering eating habits. The study concluded that influencer-led body-positivity content exerts a dual influence, fostering empowerment for some students while reinforcing narrow beauty ideals and prompting behaviours linked to disordered eating in others. It recommended that universities implement media-literacy programmes to enhance critical consumption of influencer content, promote genuine body diversity in social media campaigns and integrate routine screening for disordered eating into student health services.

Keywords: Body Positivity, Social Media, Eating Disorder Risk, Influencer, Social Media

Introduction

Body positivity is a socio-cultural movement that promotes acceptance of all body types and challenges narrow beauty ideals (Tiggemann & Anderberg, 2019). On platforms like Instagram, TikTok and YouTube, influencers and users share messages of self-acceptance through unfiltered images and personal narratives (Toluwani, 2024). While

such content can empower, research cautions that it may also reinforce appearance-focused comparisons or unrealistic ideals (Aparicio-Martínez *et al* 2019).

In Nigeria, social media play a central role in shaping beauty perceptions and self-worth. Western-influenced ideals slim physiques and lighter skin dominate online spaces, often eroding self-esteem and driving risky behaviours such as restrictive dieting (Adekeye & Agoha, 2016; Koleoso, 2018). Studies among undergraduates across Lagos and Nsukka consistently link social media exposure with body dissatisfaction and disordered eating (Olatona, 2024; Nnamchi *et al* 2024). At the same time, Nigerian influencers and celebrities like Monalisa Stephen, Etinosa Idemudia, and Enioluwa Adeoluwa amplify body-positivity messages, using relatability and storytelling to shape youth attitudes (Kelechukwu, 2024; Adeoluwa, 2025).

Despite this dual role, little research isolates the specific effects of influencer-led body positivity content. Existing work tends to examine generalised media imagery rather than how body-positive posts might reduce or, paradoxically, worsen disordered eating risks. This study addresses that gap by investigating the effect of influencer-led body positivity content on eating disorder risk among undergraduates in Osun State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does exposure to influencer-led body positivity content on social media influence body image perception among Osun State University and Redeemer's University undergraduates?
2. What is the relationship between the frequency of viewing influencer-led body positivity posts and the risk of developing disordered eating behaviours?
3. How do Osun State University and Redeemer's University undergraduates interpret influencer-driven body positivity messages on social media platforms?
4. What specific elements do influencer body positivity posts contribute to either reducing or increasing eating disorder vulnerability among young Nigerian social media users?

Body Positivity Movement on Nigerian social space

Body positivity is defined as a social and cultural movement that challenges narrow beauty standards while promoting the acceptance of diverse body shapes, sizes, abilities, ages and skin tones (Cwynar-Horta, 2016). Emerging from the fat acceptance movement of the 1960s and 1970s, alongside disability and queer activism, the movement primarily seeks to dismantle societal narratives that equate worth with appearance (Cohen, Newton-John, & Slater, 2019). Initially rooted in radical grassroots activism, body positivity has since broadened into a wider cultural discourse on self-acceptance and representation (Brewis, Wutich, & Mahdavi, 2020). In the Nigerian context, these conversations intersect with localised beauty norms shaped by indigenous aesthetics, colonial legacies, and globalised media standards, with Western ideals propagated through platforms such as Instagram and television contributing to body image concerns among youth (Adebayo,

2022). The goals of the body positivity movement include countering stigma, fostering self-love, and ensuring inclusivity in representation (Tiggemann & Zaccardo, 2018). However, the rise of digital media has transformed activism, shifting the movement from grassroots organising to influencer-led narratives on platforms such as Instagram and TikTok (Cwynar-Horta, 2016). Influencers frequently merge empowerment discourses with branding and commercial partnerships, thereby shaping contemporary body positivity content (Brewis *et al* 2020). Within Nigeria, plus-size influencers, fitness coaches and lifestyle bloggers have emerged as prominent voices, leveraging hashtags such as #BodyPositive to promote both self-love and marketable products across Snapchat, Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube (Adebayo, 2022).

Role of Social Media Influencers in Shaping Behaviour

Social media influencers (SMIs) shape public attitudes, lifestyle practices and body image by leveraging credibility, authenticity, and parasocial relationships (Abidin & Ots, 2023; Bakhshi, 2023). While they can promote positive behaviours, such as fitness participation and mental health awareness, they also risk spreading harmful norms, misinformation, and unrealistic appearance standards (Brown & Tiggemann, 2022; Kay & Rege, 2024). Perceived authenticity is central to trust and behavioural compliance, with factors such as informational value and similarity enhancing engagement, whereas overt commercialisation undermines credibility (Abidin & Ots, 2023; Bakhshi, 2023). However, authenticity is fragile, as sponsorship disclosures or perceived hypocrisy can erode trust, highlighting the need for further research on its cultural and temporal dynamics (Kay & Rege, 2024).

Digital Media and Body Image

Digital media platforms such as Instagram, Snapchat, TikTok and YouTube have become central to shaping appearance ideals and self-perception among adolescents and young adults (Tiggemann & Zaccardo, 2018). The highly visual and algorithm-driven nature of these platforms amplifies social comparison, which has been consistently associated with body dissatisfaction, low self-esteem, and disordered eating behaviours (Holland & Tiggemann, 2016; Fardouly *et al* 2018). Meta-analytic and experimental studies demonstrate that exposure to idealised body types thin and toned physiques for women and muscular physiques for men produces declines in body satisfaction, negative mood and stronger drives for thinness or muscularity, particularly among individuals with high appearance-ideal internalisation (Groesz, Levine, & Murnen, 2021; Tiggemann & Zaccardo, 2018). In contrast, research suggests that exposure to diverse or body-positive representations can yield modest improvements in body satisfaction and self-compassion (Halliwell *et al* 2015; Tiggemann *et al* 2020; Cohen *et al* 2019). However, these benefits are often moderated by pre-existing body concerns and diminished when diversity is presented in curated or sexualised ways (Cohen *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, the widespread use of beautifying filters and image-editing applications among young users has been linked to increased self-objectification, reduced appearance satisfaction and

greater interest in cosmetic surgery (McLean *et al* 2015; Ramphul & Mejias, 2018; Alsaggaf, 2021).

Review of Empirical Studies

A growing body of research highlights the significant role of social media, particularly platforms like Instagram, in shaping body image perceptions and self-esteem among young people. Chiazor, Chinelo & Obi (2024) investigated the influence of Instagram on body image and self-esteem among students, revealing that exposure to idealised celebrity images fosters body comparison, which negatively impacts self-esteem. Chiazor *et al* (2024) emphasised the need for social media literacy campaigns that promote body positivity and self-acceptance, especially among young females, suggesting structured awareness programmes on self-esteem, self-recognition, and confidence-building as preventive strategies. Jemisenia (2019) examined the effects of local female celebrity Instagram images on body satisfaction and self-esteem among young Nigerian women. Interestingly, the study reported that participants experienced the highest self-esteem and body satisfaction after viewing thin-ideal images, while exposure to plump-ideal and neutral images led to reduced satisfaction.

In contrast, Amondarain (2024) explored the impact of influencer-generated body-positive and fitness inspiration content on youth body image. The study found that such content, particularly from influencers advocating for fitness and body positivity, positively influenced youths' body self-perception, suggesting that influencers can serve as agents of positive body image reinforcement, depending on the nature of the content disseminated. Building on this, Priska *et al* (2025) conducted a 22-day longitudinal study to assess the sustained effects of body-positive and fitness-inspirational content on weight satisfaction, healthy eating and physical activity among university students. Their findings revealed that both content types improved weight satisfaction and healthy eating behaviours over time, although no significant long-term effects on exercise behaviour were detected. Amondarain (2024) examined how influencer-generated body-positive and fitness inspiration content affects youth body image. The study found that content from influencers who promote fitness and body positivity can positively impact young people's self-perception regarding their bodies. These findings suggest that influencers have the potential to act as advocates for positive body image, depending on the type of content they share.

Building on this research, Priska, Breves, Zeph, Berlo, Lauranna, Teunissen, Lars, König, Binder & Brigitte (2025) conducted a 22-day longitudinal study to evaluate the lasting effects of body-positive and fitness-inspirational content on weight satisfaction, healthy eating, and physical activity among university students. Their findings indicated that both types of content improved weight satisfaction and healthy eating behaviours over time. Umakanth (2025) examined the influence of viral social media influencers on body positivity and self-acceptance among Gen-Z audiences. The study highlighted that such influencers can foster greater body satisfaction and mental well-being by normalising diverse body types and promoting inclusive beauty norms. However, the authors cautioned that influencer content may inadvertently propagate new appearance

ideals, thus complicating the relationship between exposure to body-positive messages and actual body acceptance outcomes. Therefore, while these studies collectively demonstrate that influencer-led content has the potential to shape body image and related health behaviours, few have directly investigated its impact on eating disorder risk, particularly in the Nigerian context. Most prior research, including that of Chiazor *et al* (2024) and Jemisenia (2019), centres on self-esteem and body satisfaction without extending to disordered eating patterns. Moreover, although Priska *et al* (2025) and Amondarain (2024) provide evidence for the beneficial effects of body-positive messaging, these findings stem largely from Western populations, limiting their cultural applicability to Nigeria. This gap underscores the necessity of the present study, which specifically investigates the effect of influencer-led body positivity content on social media on eating disorder risk among university undergraduates in Osun State, Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study draws on objectification theory and cultivation theory. Objectification theory, proposed by Fredrickson & Roberts (1997), explains how media and cultural influences encourage individuals to internalise an observer's perspective of their bodies. Constant exposure to appearance-focused content fosters self-objectification, leading to body dissatisfaction, anxiety, and disordered eating. This is relevant here, as influencer-led body positivity content, though intended to empower, may still reinforce appearance ideals. Studies show that such content can temporarily boost satisfaction but also maintain pressures of body surveillance and self-objectification (Tiggemann & Zaccardo, 2015; Cohen, Newton-John, & Slater, 2019). Cultivation theory (Gerbner & Gross, 1976) further suggests that repeated exposure to media shapes perceptions of reality. In social media contexts, influencers act as "cultivating agents," promoting beauty and fitness ideals that audiences internalise over time. Among Nigerian youths, this process may normalise Westernised beauty standards, shaping body expectations and eating behaviours, as supported by evidence linking social media use with heightened body image concerns (Fardouly & Vartanian, 2016).

Method and Materials

A quantitative research design was adopted for this study, while a survey was adopted as a method. The study population comprised undergraduate students from Osun State University and Redeemer's University. The justification for choosing this population is that students represent a demographic group highly active on social media and frequently exposed to influencer content (Oko-Epelle, 2022). Additionally, Koleoso *et al* (2018) argued that young adults are vulnerable to the effects of body image messaging, making this population relevant for this study. The population consists of about 7,500 students from Redeemers University and 21,300 students, totaling 28,800 (source: Admission Office).

A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for the study. At the first stage, three out of the eight faculties in Redeemer's University were selected (Faculty of Management Sciences, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Faculty of Social Sciences). In

contrast, three colleges from seven were selected from Osun State University (College of Health Sciences, College of Science, Engineering and Technology and College of Law). These faculties were selected using random sampling.

At the second stage, purposive sampling was adopted to select two departments from each of the faculties except for the College of Law, which had only one. These departments are: Accounting, Marketing, Computer Science, Geology, Mass Communication, Psychology, Nursing Science, Physiology, Biological Sciences, Civil Engineering and Law. Stratified sampling was used to select respondents from each department using this formula:

$$\text{Sample size for strata 1} = \frac{(\text{Strata 1 population}) \times \text{Total sample size}}{\text{Total population}}$$

To determine the sample size Araoye (2004) was adopted to arrive at a sample size of 395.

Table 1: Sample allocation in to Strata

Department	Pop.	% of Pop.	Sample Size
Marketing	51	1.17%	5
Computer Science	350	8.01%	32
Accounting	33	0.76%	3
Geology	267	6.11%	24
Mass Communication	855	19.57%	77
Psychology	256	5.86%	23
Nursing Science	552	12.63%	50
Physiology	459	10.50%	41
Biological Sciences	623	14.26%	56
Law	924	21.14%	84

The instrument for data collection is the questionnaire, while IBM SPSS version 25. The data collection instrument used was a questionnaire, and data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS version 25. Of 395 distributed questionnaires, 391 were returned, resulting in a response rate of 98.9%. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, presented in the form of frequency tables and percentages. Out of the 395 copies of questionnaire-that were distributed, 391 were returned, representing 98.9%.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 2: Frequency Table Showing Demographic of Respondents

Factors	Options	Frequency	%
Age	16-18	123	31.4
	19-21	118	30.1
	22-24	109	27.8
	25 and above	41	10.4
	Total	391	100.0

Gender	Male	189	48.3
	Female	198	50.6
	Prefer not to say	4	1.0
	Total	391	100.0
University	Osun State University	250	63.9
	Redeemer's University	141	36.0
	Total	391	100.0
Faculty	Management Sciences.	8	2.0
	Natural Sciences.	56	14.3
	Social Science.	96	24.5
	College of Health Sciences.	91	23.2
	College of Science Engineering and Technology	56	14.3
	College of Law	84	21.4
	Total	391	100.0

The demographic distribution table suggests that younger adolescents, females and students from Osun State University particularly those in the social sciences were most represented in this study.

Table 3: Frequency Table Showing Exposure to Influencer-led Body Positivity Content

Factors	Options	Frequency	%
How often do you come across body positivity content led by influencers on social media?	Daily	108	27.6
	Frequently (3-5 times a week)	187	47.8
	Occasionally (1-2 times a week)	73	18.6
	Rarely (1-2 times a month)	23	5.8
	Never	0	0
	Total	391	100.0
Which platforms do you mostly see body positivity content on?	Instagram	82	20.9
	TikTok	72	18.41
	Twitter/X	23	5.8
	Facebook	54	13.8
	YouTube	49	12.5
	Snap-Chat	111	28.3
	Total	391	100.0
How often do you consciously	Always	101	25.8

change your eating habits after viewing body positivity content?	Sometimes	136	34.7
	Rarely	81	20.7
	Never	73	18.6
	Total	391	100.0
Have you ever skipped meals, fasted, or restricted your food intake because of social media content on body positivity?	Yes	306	78.2
	No	85	21.7
	Total	391	100.0
How would you describe your general interpretation of influencer-driven body positivity content?	Genuine and empowering.	121	30.9
	Motivational but unrealistic.	177	45.2
	Unrealistic and pressurising.	56	14.3
	Mixed feelings	32	8.1
	I don't pay much attention to it.	5	1.2
	Total	391	100.0

Results from table 3 imply that exposure to influencer-led body positivity content is nearly universal among participants, with Snapchat, Instagram, and TikTok serving as the main platforms of engagement. The high frequency of exposure, coupled with reported behavioural changes such as meal skipping and food restriction, suggests that such content plays a significant role in shaping eating habits and body-related practices. Although many respondents view the content as motivational, its frequent portrayal as unrealistic indicates a dual effect: it can inspire self-improvement while simultaneously reinforcing appearance pressures that may heighten disordered eating risks.

Table 4: Frequency Table Showing Relationship between Viewing Influencer-Led Body Positivity Posts and the Risk of Eating Disorder

Factors	Options	Frequency	%
How long do you typically spend viewing such posts per session?	Less than 5 minutes	156	39.8
	5–15 minutes	136	34.7
	15–30 minutes	59	15.0
	More than 30 minutes	41	10.4
	Total	391	100.0
How often do you engage (like, comment, share) with body positivity content?	Always	158	40.4
	sometimes	113	28.9
	Rarely	86	21.9
	Never	34	8.6
	Total	391	100.0
Have you ever done any of the following after viewing body	Skipped meals	108	27.6
	Started	157	40.1

image-related content?	diETING/restrictive eating		
	Felt guilty after eating	80	20.4
	Binge eaten	31	7.9
	None of the above	15	3.8
	Total	391	100.0
How often do you feel dissatisfied with your body after viewing influencer body positivity posts?	Always	44	11.2
	Sometimes	169	43.2
	Rarely	156	39.8
	Never	22	5.6
	Total	391	100.0
How often do you compare your body to those seen in body positivity content online?	Always	168	42.9
	Sometimes	134	34.2
	Rarely	74	18.9
	Never	15	3.8
	Total	391	100.0

Findings in the table above suggest that frequent exposure to influencer-led body positivity posts may heighten vulnerability to disordered eating behaviours, as many participants reported dieting, meal skipping and guilt after eating. The high levels of body dissatisfaction and constant body comparison further indicate that such content, while framed as body positive, may reinforce harmful appearance pressures and increase the risk of eating disorders.

Table 5: Frequency Table Showing Interpretation of Influencer-driven Positivity Messages

Factors	Options	Frequency	%
How do you usually feel after viewing body positivity content posted by influencers	Inspired	103	26.3
	Empowered	51	13.0
	Pressured	100	25.5
	Motivated	105	26.8
	Indifferent	32	8.1
	Total	391	100.0
How would you describe the tone of most influencer body positivity messages?	Genuine and relatable	108	27.6
	Commercial and promotional	111	28.3
	Encouraging but unrealistic	122	31.2
	Overly idealistic	50	12
	Total	391	100.0
What influences how you interpret body positivity messages by influencers?	The influencer's body type.	223	57.0
	The language and tone used.	22	5.6

Personal experience	64	16.3
Whether the post feels authentic	31	7.9
The number of likes/comments	51	13.0
Total	391	100.0

Findings in table 5 imply that while influencer-driven body positivity messages can inspire and motivate audiences, their impact is often shaped by perceptions of authenticity and relatability. The fact that many participants view such messages as encouraging yet unrealistic highlights a potential gap between the ideals promoted online and achievable realities. Additionally, the strong influence of an influencer’s body type on interpretation suggests that body positivity messages may still perpetuate appearance-based standards, limiting their effectiveness in fostering genuine acceptance.

Table 6: Frequency Table Showing Specific Elements of Influencer Body Positivity Posts Contribute to either Reducing or Increasing Eating Disorder

Factors	Options	Frequency	%
What types of posts are more likely to influence your eating habits?	Weight-loss success stories.	119	30.4
	Unfiltered, natural body images.	102	26.0
	Fitness challenges or “body goals” posts	86	21.9
	Posts showing body diversity and self-love	54	13.8
	Diet or nutrition tips from influencers	30	7.6
	Total	391	100.0
What body types do you most commonly see in influencer body positivity content?	Slim	103	26.3
	Curvy	107	27.3
	Plus-size	73	18.6
	Muscular	108	27.6
	Total	391	100.0
How do you usually judge whether a body positivity post is “authentic”?	Shows unedited or unfiltered photos	132	33.7
	Share personal struggle.	103	26.2
	Doesn’t promote products.	111	28.3
	Posts regularly without seeming scripted.	45	11.5
	Total	391	100.0

Findings in table 6 imply that not all body positivity content reduces eating disorder risk; rather, certain formats may inadvertently reinforce appearance pressures. Posts emphasising weight loss success stories, fitness goals, and muscular or slim body types may heighten body dissatisfaction and disordered eating behaviours by framing body

positivity through achievement-oriented or appearance-based ideals. Conversely, unfiltered images, genuine self-disclosures and content that avoids product promotion are perceived as more authentic, which may better support healthy body image. The low visibility of plus-size bodies also highlights a lack of true diversity in influencer content, potentially limiting inclusivity and undermining the movement's original intent.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the effects of influencer-led body-positivity content on body image and disordered eating risk among Nigerian undergraduates. Almost all respondents reported frequent exposure, mostly on Snapchat, Instagram, and TikTok. Perceptions of the content were mixed: while some viewed it as empowering, many described it as motivational but unrealistic or even pressurising. These findings highlight the double-edged nature of body-positivity content, which can inspire self-acceptance yet simultaneously reinforce appearance pressures (Tiggemann & Anderberg, 2020).

Also, Behavioural outcomes reinforce this tension. A large proportion of respondents reported dieting, skipping meals, or feeling guilty after eating, with many engaging in frequent body comparisons. This aligns with social comparison theory (Festinger, 1954) and objectification theory (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997), suggesting that influencer content provides powerful comparison targets that intensify body monitoring and dissatisfaction. The fact that respondents often judged credibility by influencer body type underscores how body-positivity narratives may paradoxically reinforce narrow ideals.

From a cultivation perspective (Gerbner & Gross, 1976), repeated exposure to curvy and muscular body types as “positive” ideals may normalise limited beauty standards, while weight-loss and fitness “goal” posts were most likely to shape eating behaviours. Conversely, authenticity cues such as unedited photos and personal struggle narratives were more positively received, indicating that transparency and relatability may buffer some of the risks.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The findings of this study have showed that while influencer-led body-positivity content is widely consumed and sometimes empowering, it often reinforces unrealistic beauty standards and contributes to disordered eating behaviours such as dieting, meal-skipping, and guilt-related eating. Students' reactions ranged from inspiration to pressure, with influencer body type strongly shaping interpretation. These findings highlight the dual role of such content in promoting inclusion while perpetuating social comparison and appearance-related pressures. It is recommended that universities and public health agencies implement media literacy programmes and support campaigns that promote authentic body diversity to counter narrow beauty ideals.

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